

Original Research Report

Facilitating Smooth Post-School Transition for Learners with Specific Learning Needs: Policy and Curriculum Recommendations

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Abstract: This study explores the complex landscape of inclusive education for learners with Specific Learning Needs (SLNs), examining critical factors that facilitate successful post-school transitions. The study employed a qualitative interpretive case study design. Conducted in Bulawayo Central District's two secondary schools with Resource Units, the research uses an innovative conceptual framework integrating Neurodiversity theory and Schlossberg's career transition theory. Through a comprehensive investigation involving ten learners with SLNs, two teachers, one school administrator, and the District Remedial Resource Tutor (DRRT), the study uncovers key strategies for supporting educational and vocational adaptation. The study adhered to ethical protocols; obtained university clearance, provincial and district permissions, and acquired informed consent from participants and parents of minors. The research reveals a multifaceted approach to enhancing educational and transitional support for the learners, highlighting critical areas for intervention: redesigning the curriculum to accommodate the diverse abilities and needs of the learners; developing a transition policy that is specifically designed to support individuals with special conditions in post-school settings; introducing corporate tax incentives for companies that create employment opportunities for individuals with special conditions and societal attitude transformation. By prioritizing stakeholder perspectives, the study develops a nuanced transitional model that offers practical guidance for more effective inclusive educational practices. The findings underscore the importance of holistic support in empowering learners with SLNs to achieve academic, social, and economic success.

Keywords: Inclusive education, Neurodiversity, Specific Learning Needs, Stakeholders, Transition services

1. Introduction

Inclusive education is a critical pathway for learners with specific learning needs (SLNs) to transition smoothly from school to adult life. The study investigates factors that promote seamless transition for learners with SLNs in Bulawayo Central District's secondary schools receiving support in Resource Units. This study, anchored in the intersection of Neurodiversity and Schlossberg's transition theories, explores stakeholder perspectives on policy and curriculum interventions that recognize and leverage neurological diversity while facilitating successful post-school transitions. The integrated theoretical lens examines how institutional structures can be transformed to honor neurodivergent capabilities rather than merely accommodating perceived deficits. Zimbabwe's educational and transitional support services for learners with special needs are outlined. The research methodology and study findings are also presented. Ultimately, the study develops a nuanced transitional model that reflects stakeholders' insights, providing a roadmap for more effective strategies that promote the smooth transition of such learners to post-school settings.

Specific Learning Needs (SLNs) are neurodevelopmental conditions that impact brain function, shaping individuals' cognitive processes, perceptions of their environment, and social interactions. According to Sapiets (2021), SLNs are acknowledged globally as a diverse group of academic skill deficits. Learners with SLNs fail to achieve conventional benchmarks in various domains, including oral communication, listening skills, written communication, fundamental reading abilities, reading fluency, reading comprehension, mathematical calculations, and problem-solving in mathematics (Grigorenko et al., 2020).

Inclusive education represents an educational philosophy and methodology that ensures all learners with special needs such as SLNs are afforded membership within the community, along with enhanced opportunities for academic, social engagement, and economic success (Sibanda, 2018). Inclusive education plays a crucial role in preparing learners with special needs for post-school life by providing opportunities to develop social skills, self-advocacy, and practical experiences within a supportive mainstream environment. Thereby facilitating a smoother and more confident transition to adult life and potential employment. The process of transition involves the movement of the learners from school to community integration, participation in the workforce, enrolment in post-secondary educational institutions, and other critical elements of adult life, such as financial literacy, travel, and the development of social relationships (Wehman et al., 2020). In this context, post-school educational and transition services refer to the services available for learners with special needs that prepare them for a smooth transition from their academic institutions into adult life (Rao, 2024). Such services are designed to be learner-centered, highlighting learners' strengths, preferences, interests, abilities, and potential rather than focusing on their weaknesses (Strnadová et al., 2023). This approach demands a collaborative framework in which learners are meaningfully involved in the planning and decision-making stages (Strnadová et al., 2023).

In Zimbabwe, educational and transitional support services for learners with special needs are offered through an inclusive education framework. Currently, the country does not have specific legislation on inclusive education (Chitiyo & Dzenga, 2021). However, its draft policy characterizes

inclusive education as a methodology aimed at guaranteeing universal access to and engagement in education for all learners. This is achieved by integrating responsive, learner-centered support to address the specific barriers that hinder learners from fully participating in educational environments and being supported to realize their potential (Chataika & Hlatywayo, 2022).

There are recent policies that support and promote the inclusion of learners with special needs. The Education Amendment Act 2020, alongside the Zimbabwe National Disability Policy 2021, represents important advancements in educational rights (Chakaita & Hlatywayo, 2022). The former guarantees that every citizen and permanent resident of Zimbabwe is entitled to a basic education funded by the state, which includes provisions for adult basic education. Meanwhile, the latter policy ensures that individuals with special needs are exempt from all fees and levies at public educational establishments (Chakaita & Hlatywayo, 2022). Additionally, the Secretary's Circular number P36 of 2023, which cancelled and replaced Circular Number P36 of October 1990, provides a standard procedure for the establishment and management of support facilities for ensuring inclusive access to and full participation in primary and secondary education for learners with special needs in primary and secondary schools (Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education [MoPSE], n.d). Educational and transitional support services are meticulously crafted to address the unique challenges faced by learners with special needs. The goal is to empower learners with the skills, knowledge, and adaptive strategies necessary for successful independent living and professional development beyond their academic journey. In the following discussion, five types of educational and transitional provisions available to learners with special needs are explored.

Inclusive schools are mainstream educational settings that accommodate all learners, integrating learners with and without special needs in shared classrooms. This approach, termed "unplanned" or "de facto" inclusion (Chakaita & Hlatywayo, 2022), often occurs when parents place children with special needs in schools without institutional documentation of their specific conditions. Despite the perception of providing specialized care, these environments do not always effectively address the diverse needs of learners with special requirements (Tlou & Nyoni, 2021). According to a UNESCO report in Zimbabwe (2023), while 19.04% of primary school learners are identified as having SLNs, this percentage drops sharply to 9.20% at the secondary level. This dramatic decline suggests that many learners who received support services in primary school may be placed under de facto inclusion without the specialized accommodations they require. Special schools utilize a twin-track curriculum, adapting mainstream education to accommodate individual learning needs while providing a school-based curriculum (Chakaita & Hlatshwayo, 2022). In some mainstream settings, learners with special needs are grouped in specialized classes, ideally managed by special needs teachers, and initially intended to serve learners with specific conditions like hearing or visual impairments. However, due to resource constraints, specialized classes now often group learners with diverse conditions and educational levels. Some special schools have transitioned to reverse inclusion, welcoming learners without special needs and implementing inclusive pedagogical approaches. Resource units within mainstream schools serve as specialized centers, offering targeted support and adapted materials, enabling learners with special needs to learn alongside peers while receiving periodic specialized

instruction (Chakaita & Hlatwayo, 2022).

The global landscape of research on transition frameworks, models, and theories has progressed over time. However, there is a significant lack of focused investigations that provide evidence for better practices, particularly concerning the post-secondary outcomes of individuals with special needs (Bam et al., 2023). While research on educational and transitional services for learners with special needs is emerging in Zimbabwe, literature on transition services for learners with special needs remains sparse, with the limited available research focusing on physically impaired learners. This intensifies the existing scholarly gap in understanding the experiences of learners with neurodevelopmental conditions, particularly those with SLNs supported in Resource units. Previous studies have explored specific aspects of special education and transition services, such as Hlatwayo and Ncube (2014)'s investigation into transitional services for deaf learners and their community participation skills, Mpofu (2018)'s assessment of transitional services for learners with disabilities in secondary schools, and Maposa (2020)'s examination of employment prospects for deaf learners. These studies reveal a notable limitation: they address physical impairment categories, with minimal in-depth exploration of learners with neurodevelopmental conditions like SLNs.

The existing literature lacks comprehensive insights into the unique educational and transitional support needs of secondary school learners with SLN who receive support in Resource units. This gap is particularly significant because neurodevelopmental conditions present distinct educational and transitional challenges that may differ from those of physically impaired learners. The limited scholarship fails to provide a holistic understanding of how educational and transitional services can effectively support the academic, social, and career development of learners with SLNs. Against this background, this study aims to address the critical gap by examining stakeholders' perspectives on educational and transitional services for secondary school learners with SLNs receiving support in Resource units. By exploring these perspectives, the research seeks to generate nuanced insights that can inform more targeted and effective support strategies, bridging the current knowledge deficit in understanding the comprehensive needs of learners with neurodevelopmental conditions in the Zimbabwean educational context.

1.1. Statement of Problem

The existing education and post-school research landscape in Zimbabwe reveals a critical knowledge gap concerning learners with SLNs supported in Resource Units. Despite the growing emphasis on inclusive education, there is a significant lack of comprehensive research exploring the educational and transitional support services for secondary school learners with neurodevelopmental conditions such as SLNs. Current literature focuses on learners with physical impairments, leaving the unique challenges and needs of learners with SLNs unaddressed. This scholarly deficit undermines the development of targeted support strategies that could effectively facilitate these learners' academic, social, and vocational transitions. Consequently, there is an urgent need to systematically investigate stakeholders' perspectives to generate nuanced insights into the comprehensive support requirements of learners with SLNs, thereby informing more responsive and inclusive educational and post-school

practices.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

This research examines stakeholders' insights into factors that facilitate the smooth transition of learners with SLNs supported in Resource Units to post-school settings.

Specifically, the study sought to find out:

- (a) Policy and curriculum interventions that enhance post-school transition opportunities for learners with SLNs.

1.3. Research Question

The following research question guided the study:

- (a) What policy and curriculum interventions do stakeholders propose to enhance post-school transition opportunities for learners with SLNs?

1.4. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework combines Neurodiversity theory and Schlossberg's career transition theory. Neurodiversity, introduced by Judy Singer, reframes neurological variations as a natural aspect of human genetic diversity (Mirfin-Veitch et al., 2020). The theory challenges deficit-based perspectives by positioning neurodivergent individuals as different, not deficient, and argues that societal expectations can create disabling environments (Shaw et al., 2024). Epistemologically, it advocates for centering neurodivergent perspectives, prioritizing community experiences and social justice in knowledge creation. Schlossberg et al., (1995) define transition theory as a framework for understanding neurodiverse learners' experiences, defining transition as a dynamic period of change in relationships, routines, and roles. Complemented by Neurodiversity theory, this integrated perspective emphasizes the unique challenges in school-to-post-school transitions (Mokhtar et al., 2024). The approach advocates for a support model that moves beyond mere accommodation, focusing on empowering neurodiverse learners by recognizing and valuing their distinctive neurological capabilities.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study utilized a qualitative interpretive methodology to explore educational and transitional services for learners with SLNs in secondary settings. A single case study design focusing on the Bulawayo Central District in Zimbabwe was used. This design enabled comprehensive exploration of a specific issue within its defined context (Coombs, 2022). This approach facilitates an in-depth investigation of intricate matters, with the researcher's prior knowledge of the district facilitating a thorough examination and establishing meaningful participant connections.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

In January 2016, an introductory letter was received from the Department of Educational Foundations, Management, and Curriculum Studies at Midlands State University. This correspondence

requested authorization to carry out research within the Bulawayo Metropolitan Province. Approval for the research in the Bulawayo Central district was later obtained from the Central District Education Officer (DEO). Additionally, consent was granted by the heads of schools. Informed consent forms were provided to participants, requiring parental signatures for the learners, with only two participants under 18. Questionnaires were distributed directly to Resource unit teachers, while focus group discussions were held with the learners. Interviews were carried out with the school administrator and the DRRT.

All data collected during the research was treated with strict confidentiality. Participant identities were protected through a coding system, with personal identifiers removed from all documentation and replaced with unique identification numbers. Digital data, including interview recordings and transcripts, was stored on password-protected devices, with access restricted to the researcher. Physical documents, including signed consent forms and completed questionnaires, were kept in a locked cabinet in a secure office.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was carried out in two of the ten government secondary schools in Bulawayo central district in Zimbabwe. These are the only mainstream secondary schools with Resource units supporting learners with SLNs in the district.

Thus, the selection of two schools represents a complete sample rather than a limitation, as these institutions constitute the entire population of secondary schools with resource units in the Bulawayo Central District. This comprehensive inclusion strengthens the study by providing complete coverage of the phenomenon within the district, enabling in-depth examination of all available resource units, and allowing thorough investigation of educational and transition support services in all available settings.

2.3. Population and Sample

The research used purposive sampling to select participants from government secondary schools with resource units in the Bulawayo Central District. Out of ten schools, only two had resource units. Focusing on the lower secondary level, participants included five learners with SLNs from each of the two schools, two teachers, school administrators, and the DRRT. One school administrator withdrew due to scheduling constraints.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

The study employed qualitative data collection methods to gather insights into post-school transition factors for learners with SLNs. Data collection began in April 2016, utilizing unstructured interviews, open-ended questionnaires, and focus group discussions (FGDs). Interviews were conducted with the DRRT and the school administrator, questionnaires were distributed to teachers, and FGDs were organized with learners. Voice recorders were used, and participants were encouraged to communicate in their preferred language, fostering an open and comfortable research environment.

The study implemented rigorous measures to ensure data quality and trustworthiness. Multiple triangulation strategies were employed, including methodological triangulation through diverse data collection methods (interviews, questionnaires, and FGDs), and data source triangulation across

different stakeholder groups (learners, teachers, the school administrator, and the DRRT). The use of participants' preferred language enhanced response accuracy.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. Following data transcription and translation to English, analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach: familiarization with the data through repeated reading, generating initial codes, collating codes into potential themes, reviewing and refining themes, and defining and naming final themes. This iterative process ensured systematic interpretation of the data, resulting in a coherent thematic framework.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the study's results, beginning with an age distribution table of the ten learners with SLNs. Subsequently, the perspectives of key stakeholders, including teachers, the DRRT, and the school administrator, on factors facilitating smoother post-school transitions were examined.

Table 1: Age distribution of learners with SLNs

Participant	Age
Learner A	16
Learner B	17
Learner C	18
Learner D	18
Learner E	18
Learner F	18
Learner G	18
Learner H	19
Learner I	23
Learner J	25

Table 1 reveals the age distribution of learners with SLNs, contrasting with the Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency (ZIMSTAT) 2020 report. While ZIMSTAT defines the school-age population as 3-18 years, with the 19-24 age group expected to be in tertiary education, the study shows learners aged 19, 23, and 25 in the lower secondary level. This anomaly suggests significant systemic barriers to education and post-school transition, highlighting critical gaps in inclusive education infrastructure and support mechanisms for learners with SLNs.

The stakeholders proposed comprehensive strategies to enhance existing educational and transitional services. Their collaborative insights aim to develop targeted interventions that address

multifaceted barriers preventing seamless transitions to post-school environments, empowering learners to achieve greater independence and success.

The DRRT's perspectives:

- *"...Curriculum for Special Needs Education must be designed. The curriculum must promote Individualized Teaching Programs..."*
- *"...Credentials and certificates must be awarded to learners with SLNs so that they have something to present to employers..."*
- *"...the government must formulate transitional frameworks which will facilitate learners' smooth transition from secondary to post-secondary settings..."*
- *"...it all begins with the change of attitude towards the learners within the government. The government must employ learners with SLNs in various ministries at least as general workers...then the private sector will do likewise."*

The School Head's views:

- *"...there must be transitional policies*
- *"a new curriculum must be designed..."*
- *"...Teachers need the motivation to deal with such learners...teaching these learners is a difficult task and hence the government would intervene through giving these teachers incentives so that they work extra mile..."*

Teachers' views:

- *"a new curriculum must be designed, and the curriculum must be attuned to the needs and abilities of different learners.'*
- *"Learners must write external examinations that are within their IQ levels and capabilities. This will motivate learners to learn...failure demotivates children..."*
- *"These learners need basic arithmetic, writing, and reading skills so that they just "appreciate" academic skills..."*
- *...the government can introduce tax rebate to all companies that reserve certain posts and ranks for learners with SLNs ... this will act as an incentive for companies to employ more people with disabilities..."*

The findings reveal a comprehensive, multi-stakeholder approach to improving educational and transitional services for learners with SLNs. The proposed solutions converge on several critical themes: curriculum redesign, policy development, employment opportunities, and societal attitude transformation. Central to these recommendations is the urgent need for a specialized, individualized curriculum that is flexible and attuned to learners' diverse needs and abilities.

The lower secondary level is widely recognized as the minimum qualification essential for entering the formal job market or advancing to tertiary education (Gatsi et al., 2020). Therefore, it represents a critical threshold that provides access to numerous life opportunities (Gatsi et al., 2020). Stakeholders strongly advocate systematic policy interventions to facilitate smoother transitions from secondary to

post-secondary settings. This entails developing appropriate curricula, credentials, and external examinations that align with learners' cognitive capabilities. Teachers frequently encounter challenges in delivering instructional material and implementing curriculum structures that adequately address the needs of learners with SLNs (Ahammed, 2021). In 2015, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education (MoPSE) in Zimbabwe introduced a competency-based curriculum, which emphasizes the acquisition of skills, abilities, personality traits, capacities, knowledge, and values (Mpofu & Sefotho, 2024). However, this curriculum's implementation has proven particularly challenging for learners with SLNs and teachers. Significant obstacles include resource limitations, poor collaborative efforts, and insufficient teacher preparation (Mpofu & Sefotho, 2024). UNICEF (2023) reports that the Zimbabwean education system remains academic-oriented, consequently constraining the potential of learners who excel in practical and technical skills. Curriculum challenges are further compounded by inadequate accommodations and support from the Zimbabwe School Examinations Council (ZIMSEC). Learners with SLNs are required to sit for external examinations under the same conditions as their typically developing peers without receiving appropriate accommodation or support. Despite the availability of examination provisions, school administrators often fail to identify and apply for necessary accommodations for these learners (*Special Needs – ZIMSEC*, n.d.). This systemic oversight significantly increases the likelihood of poor academic performance among learners with SLNs, potentially limiting their future educational and professional opportunities by restricting their ability to obtain critical credentials for accessing the job market.

Employment represents a critical pathway for social inclusion, with stakeholders advocating for transitional policies that support learners moving from secondary school to the workforce. By framing employment as a fundamental right and opportunity, these proposals seek to dismantle perceptual barriers that have traditionally excluded learners with SLNs. Zimbabwe has established legal and institutional frameworks, such as the Disabled Persons Act, intended to protect the rights of individuals with special needs. However, the government has demonstrated limited commitment to ensuring the effective implementation of these laws (Mandipa, 2013). Critically, Zimbabwe lacks a comprehensive transition policy specifically designed to support individuals with special needs in post-school settings (Ncube & Hlatwayo, 2014). The National Youth Policy (NYP), initially introduced in 2000 and revised in 2013, represents the only existing policy addressing transitional services (Hlungwani et al., 2021). While the policy outlines strategies to empower local youth and includes provisions for youth with special needs, it lacks crucial specificity regarding governmental support for post-school opportunities (Mpofu, 2018). The policy's one-size-fits-all approach potentially creates implementation gaps that further marginalize individuals with special needs.

In contrast, the United States has developed a more robust framework for supporting transitions. Two principal statutes—the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) and the Rehabilitation Act of 1973 (amended by the Workforce Innovation and Opportunity Act)—mandate comprehensive transition services. These legislations ensure structured support for learners and youth with special needs as they prepare for and transition into postsecondary life (United States Department of Education, 2020). The stark difference in policy approaches highlights the critical need for Zimbabwe to develop

more nuanced, targeted transition policies that genuinely address the unique challenges faced by learners with special needs. By learning from international practices, Zimbabwe could create more inclusive pathways to employment and social integration.

Extensive research has consistently highlighted the multifaceted challenges confronted by teachers when educating learners with special needs in Zimbabwe (Chitiyo et al., 2024; Khumalo, 2024; Mpofu & Sefotho, 2024; Ncube & Sedibe, 2022). Acknowledging the complexities inherent in specialized education, stakeholders underscore the paramount importance of comprehensive teacher support. The recommended strategies encompass a comprehensive approach, including targeted professional development and meaningful incentives. Through investing strategically in teachers working with learners with SLNs, this approach recognizes that meaningful educational transformation is fundamentally dependent on empowering the professionals responsible for implementing inclusive educational practices. Such a systemic approach aims to cultivate a more supportive, responsive, and adaptive educational ecosystem that can effectively address the diverse learning requirements of learners with special needs.

Figure 1: A transition model for learners with SLN

Figure 1 presents a diagrammatical representation of the insights from stakeholders to enhance educational and transitional services for learners with SLNs. The model emphasizes several key elements.

- Curriculum Design: This encompasses the educational curriculum and its adaptation to meet the unique needs of learners with SLNs.

- **Assessment & Credentials:** This component focuses on evaluating the learners' progress and providing them with appropriate credentials or certifications.
- **Societal Attitude Transformation:** The model highlights the importance of changing societal attitudes and promoting greater inclusion and acceptance of learners with SLNs.
- **Teacher Support:** Ensuring that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills and resources to effectively support learners, especially on how to handle ZIMSEC accommodations for the learners.
- **Transitional Support:** The model recognizes the need for dedicated support during the transition from school to post-school settings, such as employment or further education. A specific policy is required.
- **Employment Integration:** This element emphasizes the importance of integrating learners with SLNs into the workforce, fostering their employability and economic empowerment. Innovative strategies such as government employment quotas, tax rebates for companies employing individuals with SLNs, and concerted efforts to change societal attitudes.

The ultimate desired outcomes of this transitional model are employability, social inclusion, and economic empowerment for learners as they transition from secondary education to post-school settings. However, this study's scope was limited to two secondary schools in Bulawayo Central District, which may not fully represent the diverse experiences across Zimbabwe's educational landscape. The small sample size, while providing rich qualitative insights, may limit the generalizability of findings to broader contexts. Additionally, the research focused specifically on Resource Units, potentially overlooking the experiences of learners with neurodevelopmental conditions in other educational provisions.

The developed transitional model, grounded in stakeholders' experiences and perspectives, provides a practical framework for enhancing inclusive educational practices in Zimbabwe. This research contributes to filling the existing knowledge gap regarding learners with neurodevelopmental conditions and offers valuable insights for policymakers, teachers, and practitioners working to support learners with SLNs. Moving forward, the implementation of the proposed transitional model could significantly enhance the post-school outcomes for learners with SLNs, ensuring their successful integration into adult life and employment opportunities.

Further research should examine the Zimbabwe Schools Examination Council's (ZIMSEC) implementation of examination accommodations for learners with neurodevelopmental conditions. The current study reveals a critical gap in communication between ZIMSEC and schools regarding assessment and accommodations available for learners with SLNs. While examination accommodations are effectively provided for learners with physical challenges, those with neurodevelopmental conditions often lack adequate support due to institutional barriers and limited advocacy from schools. This disparity warrants investigation to ensure equitable assessment practices and to develop more effective protocols for identifying and supporting examination candidates with SLNs.

4. Conclusion

This research has illuminated critical perspectives on educational and transitional support services for secondary school learners with SLNs in Resource Units within Bulawayo Central District. Through a comprehensive analysis integrating Neurodiversity theory and Schlossberg's career transition theory, the study has uncovered significant insights from key stakeholders, including learners, teachers, school administrators, and support staff. Sustained effort is needed to transform societal attitudes and build a more inclusive culture that embraces learners with neurodevelopmental and physical conditions in both secondary schools and the broader community. The establishment of more resource units in secondary schools is vital to ensure the seamless continuation of support services from primary to secondary education. A comprehensive redesign of the curriculum is essential to accommodate the diverse learning abilities and needs of all learners. The implementation of a targeted transition policy would provide crucial support for individuals with special conditions as they navigate post-school environments. To enhance employment opportunities, the government should establish corporate tax incentives for companies that create inclusive workplaces for individuals with physical and neurodevelopmental conditions. Thus, the transition model developed through stakeholder consultation provides a practical framework for implementing holistic support systems that empower learners with special needs, such as SLNs, to achieve academic, social, and economic success.

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Conflict of Interest

The author declares no potential conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

All aspects of this work were done by NNN.

Data Availability Statement

The data used for this study is available based on request.

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References

- Ahammed, H. (2021). Challenges faced by teachers of learners with learning disability. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(2), 294–312.
- Bam, A., Kriger, S., & Cottle, Z. (2023). A (mis) guidance of disabled youth: Post-secondary schooling transition experiences in South Africa. *African Journal of Disability (Online)*, 12, 1–11.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in*

- Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Chataika, T., & Hlatywayo, L. (2022). Examining the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Zimbabwe. *Disability Rights and Inclusiveness in Africa: The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Challenges and Change*, 44, 79.
- Chitiyo, A., & Dzenga, C. G. (2021). Special and inclusive education in Southern Africa. *Journal of Special Education Preparation*, 1(1), 55–66.
- Coombs, H. (2022). *Case Study Research Defined*. Southern Utah University. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo>.
- Gatsi, R., Omidire, M. F., & Human-Vogel, S. (2020). Conceptualization of the Premature School Exit Phenomenon in Mashonaland Region of Zimbabwe: The Voice of Early School Leavers. *Journal of Black Psychology*, 46(2–3), 228–260. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095798420908458>
- Grigorenko, E. L., Compton, D. L., Fuchs, L. S., Wagner, R. K., Willcutt, E. G., & Fletcher, J. M. (2020). Understanding, educating, and supporting children with specific learning disabilities: 50 years of science and practice. *American Psychologist*, 75(1), 37. <https://rsa.ed.gov/sites/default/files/subregulatory/postsecondary-transition-guide-august-2020.pdf>
- ZimCO Adolescents Strategy_FINAL_Signed.indd
- Khumalo, G. (2024). *Exploring the psychosocial challenges of adolescent learners Opportunities for school-based psychosocial support in public schools*. <https://wiredspace.wits.ac.za/bitstreams/f39203f1-7744-4b0e-9e56-2c439e260fb0/download>
- Mandipa, E. (2013). A critical analysis of the legal and institutional frameworks for the realization of the rights of persons with disabilities in Zimbabwe. *Afr. Disability Rts. YB*, 1, 73.
- Maposa, D. R. (2020). *An exploratory study of the employment prospects of Deaf individuals in Zimbabwe*. <https://open.uct.ac.za/handle/11427/32521>
- Mirfin-Veitch, B., Jalota, N., & Schmidt, L. (2020). Responding to neurodiversity in the education context: An integrative literature review. *Donald Beasley Institute*, 56. <https://disabilityconnect.org.nz/wp-content/uploads/responding-to-neurodiversity-beasley-institute-1.pdf>
- Mokhtar, K., Zaharudin, R., & Ghazali, K. A. (2024). Career Transition for Special Needs Students: A Significant Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 13(1). <https://ijarped.com/index.php/journal/article/view/651>
- Mpofu, J. (2018). Exploring the effectiveness of transitional services provided to learners with disabilities in Chinhoyi urban secondary schools in Zimbabwe. http://ijessr.com/uploads/ijessr_01_62.pdf
- Mpofu, J., & Sefotho, M. M. (2024). Challenges of competency-based curriculum in teaching learners with learning disabilities. *African Journal of Disability*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ajod.v13i0.1268>
- Ncube, M., & Sedibe, M. (2022). Exploring challenges to inclusion of children with intellectual disabilities in early childhood development in Mutoko District, Zimbabwe. *International*

- Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(10), 195–211.
- Rao, S. (2024). A Journey across Countries, Constructs, and Dreams: Perspectives of Indian American Families of Youth with Developmental Disabilities on Transition from School to Post-School Settings. *American Journal of Qualitative Research*, 8(1), 133–156.
- Sapiets, S. J. (2021). *Embracing complexity in research on neurodevelopmental conditions and mental health*. <https://kar.kent.ac.uk/93151/> Page | 265
- Schlossberg, N. K., Waters, E. B., & Goodman, J. (1995). *Counseling Adults in Transition: Linking Practice with Theory*. Springer Publishing Company.
- Shaw, S. C. K., Brown, M. E., Jain, N. R., George, R. E., Bernard, S., Godfrey-Harris, M., & Doherty, M. (2024). When I say... neurodiversity paradigm. *Medical Education*. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Sebastian-Shaw/publication/385950072_When_I_say_neurodiversity_paradigm/links/673d90f0b94c451c116d54c9/When-I-say-neurodiversity-paradigm.pdf
- Sibanda, P. (2018). A review of the implementation of inclusive education in Zimbabwe: Challenges and opportunities. *Scientific Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 7(9), 808–815.
- Special Needs – Zimsec*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 20, 2024, from <https://www5.zimsec.co.zw/special-needs/>
- Strnadová, I., Danker, J., Dowse, L., & Tso, M. (2023). Supporting students with disability to improve academic, social, emotional, and self-determination and life-skills outcomes: Umbrella review of evidence-based practices. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2023.2221239>
- Tlou, F. N., & Nyoni, T. (2021). Alignments and Mismatches of Policies on Children with Learning Difficulties/Disabilities to Professional Practice Expectations in Zimbabwe: A Reality Check. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 9(8), 465–471.
- Wehman, P., Brooke, V., & Taylor, J. (2020). Introduction to transition planning. *Essentials of Transition Planning*, 1–22.
- UNESCO (2023) Addressing the needs of learners with disabilities in Zimbabwe | UNESCO <https://rsa.ed.gov/sites/default/files/subregulatory/postsecondary-transition-guide-august-2020.pdf>

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